

DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF BIOMIMETIC LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: The strength of a biomimetic CFRP laminate with a stacking sequence similar to that found in many animal hard tissues is examined. The static strength of the biomimetic laminate with holes of different diameters is compared to that of a standard quasi-isotropic and a cross-ply laminate. The first two have similar elastic moduli and strengths without a hole. The ratio of notched to unnotched strength is also nearly the same, while the cross-ply laminate has the lowest ratio. This difference is explained in terms of the extent of an equivalent damage zone, which depends on the laminate's architecture. The implications of the findings for the design of damage-tolerant laminates are discussed.

KEYWORDS: biomimetic composite, damage tolerance, notched sample, strength ratio, fracture, fiber orientation distribution

INTRODUCTION

Biological materials derive remarkable mechanical properties from their composite nature and reinforcement architecture. Many biological composites are fiber-reinforced laminates similar to plywood, with a fiber orientations that varies through their thickness in relatively constant angle steps [1-3]. As these composites often have a protective or structural function, such as in insect cuticles, it has been assumed that this fiber architecture may give them a particularly good strength or damage tolerance. If this should be the case, a biomimetic microstructure would be a way to make improved composites [3, 4]. Tests have shown that the quasi-static moduli and unnotched strength of a biomimetic and a conventional quasi-isotropic laminate are nearly the same. Gunderson and Whitney however showed that the impact resistance of the biomimetic laminate, in terms of energy and force to initiate delamination, was better than that of a standard quasi-isotropic laminate [3]. To examine the post-impact performance, this paper presents results on the quasi-static behavior of a biomimetic laminate including some damage. It examines the sensitivity of a biomimetic laminate to the presence of a damaged area, here modeled as an open hole, and compares the residual strength and the fracture patterns to those of conventional quasi-isotropic and a cross-ply laminates.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Various authors, including Neville [1], Giraud et al. [2], and Gunderson and Whitney [3] have shown examples of biological laminates with a fairly regular angle difference of about 78°

between successive plies (Fig. 1). This lamination scheme, selected for the biomimetic laminate in the present study, gives a double helical lay-up with angle steps of 24° for each helix. For a 16-ply laminate, the outermost plies are oriented at 90° with respect to each other, and the laminate is nearly quasi-isotropic.

The damage tolerance as related to the ratio of strength of a laminate with and without a hole was analyzed by the Damage Zone Criterion (DZC) approach developed by Eriksson and Aronsson [5]. The actual, two-dimensional damage in the laminate is modeled as a fictitious crack extending from the hole perpendicularly to the applied load. The residual stress acting on this crack of length d representing the damage zone is assumed to be constant. The stresses ahead of this crack correspond to a linear elastic stress distribution for an anisotropic plate:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r &= \sigma_o, \quad x \leq d \\ \sigma_r &= \frac{\sigma_a}{2} \left\{ 2 + R^2 + 3R^4 - (K_T^\infty - 3)[5R^6 - 7R^8] \right\} \quad x \geq d \\ R &= D/2x \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where σ_a is the applied stress, σ_r is the stress on the reduced section, σ_o is the strength of the laminate without hole, and D is the diameter of the hole. The stress concentration factor K_T^∞ for an infinitely wide plate depends on the laminate's elastic properties:

$$K_T^\infty = 1 + \left[\frac{2}{A_{22}} \left(\sqrt{A_{11}A_{22}} - A_{12} + \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{2A_{66}} \right) \right]^5 \tag{2}$$

where A_{ij} are the laminate stiffnesses. The elastic properties of the laminates were calculated using classical lamination theory [6]. A correction was made for the finite width of the samples. This however gives a negligible calculated difference for the sample dimensions used here and is thus not absolutely necessary. The integral of the stresses on the net section must equal the applied load:

$$\frac{\sigma_a w t}{2} = \sigma_o t d + \int_{D/2+d}^{w/2} (\sigma_o + \sigma_r - \sigma_r|_{x=D/2+d}) dx \tag{3}$$

Fig. 1: Lay-up of the biomimetic composite laminate

The critical damage zone size d^* can be calculated from this equation at the ultimate load σ_N of the sample with a hole [5]. This damage zone size is taken as an indicator of the damage

tolerance of the laminate. A larger damage zone at failure would point to a higher damage tolerance, as it gives a higher ratio of strength with a hole to strength without a hole.

EXPERIMENTAL

The samples were made from unidirectional (UD) AT400/EP carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy prepregs (Asahi Kasei Corporation, Japan). The cured material had a longitudinal modulus of 117Gpa and a transverse modulus of about 11GPa. Laminated plates consisting of 16 plies of prepreg were cured in an autoclave at a pressure of 6bar and 130°C for two hours. The samples were slow cooled under pressure by turning off the heat in the autoclave, in order to minimize internal stresses. The resulting laminates had a thickness of 1.98mm, ± 0.06 mm. The cured plates were cut into 20mm wide samples with a water-cooled rotary diamond saw. The samples were then left to stabilize at room temperature and humidity for at least one week. The lay-ups of the samples for this study are given in Table 1. Samples were tested without hole and with a central 4mm or 5mm diameter hole corresponding to a ratio of hole diameter to sample width of 1/5 and 1/4. The CFRP samples were clamped between two 5mm thick acrylic plates during drilling, in order to keep damage around the hole during machining to a minimum. The samples without and with a hole had a gauge length of 120mm and 80mm, respectively. Tapered GFRP tabs were bonded to the sample ends to reduce the likelihood of damage or slippage in the grips.

The tensile tests were conducted monotonically up to failure at a cross-head velocity of 1mm/min. For the samples without holes the extension was measured by strain gauges bonded to both sides of the samples. Strength results were accepted only for samples in which failure damage did not extend into the gripping areas. For the samples with holes, the load-extension curve and the peak force were recorded. The stress was calculated based on the full section of the sample.

Table 1: Definition of sample types

Sample	Lam. type	Laminate lay-up
CP	Cross-ply	$(0^\circ / 90^\circ)_{4s}$
QI	Quasi-isotropic	$(0^\circ / 45^\circ / 90^\circ / -45^\circ)_{2s}$
BM	Biomimetic	$(0^\circ / -78^\circ / 24^\circ / -54^\circ / 48^\circ / -30^\circ / 72^\circ / -6^\circ // -84^\circ / 18^\circ / -60^\circ / 42^\circ / -36^\circ / 66^\circ / -12^\circ / 90^\circ)$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The biomimetic and the standard quasi-isotropic laminates had nearly the same elastic modulus, while the cross-ply laminate was much stiffer (Table 2). The experimental moduli of the plain laminates are all within 5% of the predictions. The symmetric quasi-isotropic and cross-ply laminates had no extension/flexural coupling. The transverse strains on opposing surfaces of the biomimetic laminate, however, differed significantly, as the axial stress led to a bending about the longitudinal axis.

Table 2: Elastic properties of the unnotched laminates (calculated values in parentheses)

Sample	E_l [GPa]	ν	σ_o [MPa]
CP	66.47 (64.4)	0.065	901
QI	48.84 (50.8)	0.335	676
BM	49.38 (52.0) / 47.98 (52.0)*	0.320 / 0.333*	654 / 619 *

* in two normal directions, parallel to surface fibers

The unnotched laminates had a linear stress strain curve until failure. All samples failed on the free length, away from the grips. The strength of the biomimetic samples was 3-8% lower than that of the quasi-isotropic laminate. The cross-ply sample's strength was about one third higher, as a result of the higher proportion of strong 0° plies. The fractured zones had different appearances in all three samples. The cross-ply samples broke along a straight, slightly jagged line, perpendicular to the sample's axis, and damage was localized in the vicinity of the fracture. On the other hand, the damaged area in the quasi-isotropic and biomimetic laminates extended over a length corresponding to more than twice the tensile sample's width, with extensive delamination and splitting. The biomimetic laminate samples also failed in compression in the longer half of the broken sample, upon recoil at tensile failure. This happened for none of the two other laminate types, and may be due to a lower apparent compressive strength of the unsymmetric biomimetic laminate.

The notched strength, the notched-to-unnotched strength ratio, and the equivalent damage zone size calculated from the strength ratio are reported in Table 3, for laminates with two different hole diameters. The strengths of the biomimetic and quasi-isotropic laminates with a ø4mm hole were about the same. With a ø5mm hole, the biomimetic laminate had a clearly higher strength. Its strength ratio with a ø4mm or ø5mm hole was slightly over 4% higher and nearly 15% higher, respectively, than that of the quasi-isotropic laminate. Its strength was also less variable than that of the latter. Although the cross-ply laminate had a much higher unnotched strength than the others, its notched strength was just 11% higher than that of the quasi-isotropic and biomimetic laminates, and its strength ratio was almost 20% lower for a ø4mm hole. From these results, it would seem that the biomimetic laminate is slightly more tolerant to damage in the form of a hole than the quasi-isotropic laminate, and that this characteristic is more pronounced for larger hole diameters. Further tests are planned with other hole sizes, to verify this.

Table 3: Failure loads of the laminates with holes and calculated critical length of the representative damage zone. Standard deviation given in parentheses

Sample	D [mm]	σ_N [MPa]	σ_N / σ_o	d^*
CP	4.0	459.1 (14.1)	0.510	0.45
QI	4.0	407.3 (49.3)	0.603	0.89
	5.0	351.1 (26.4)	0.519	0.72
BM	4.0	399.8 (19.7)	0.628	1.01
	5.0	379.4 (18.1)	0.596	1.13

The calculated equivalent damage zone d^* at failure for the samples with the ø4mm hole was about 13% larger in the biomimetic than in the standard quasi-isotropic laminate. For a ø5mm hole, it was over 50% larger. The size of d^* for the cross-ply laminate was by far the

lowest, at less than half the value for the biomimetic laminate. The higher value of d^* indicates a more extensive lateral propagation of the damage before failure of the sample. The dependence of the extent of the damage on the laminate lay-up has been modeled by Chang et al. [6]. The present results concord with the analytical results of that group for the cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates: whereas the cross-ply samples failed suddenly, without prior sign, the development of damage in the quasi-isotropic samples was signaled by sharp, high-pitch sounds as failure approached. Although the biomimetic laminate had a similar calculated extent of damage at impending failure, d^* , as the quasi-isotropic laminate, its different reinforcement geometry is expected to lead to a different spatial distribution of the damage. The broader distribution of angles between plies and the loading direction is expected to lead to a wider range of interlaminar shear stresses near the edge and the hole, and thus to a more progressive evolution of damage. This will be investigated in the future. The stress distribution in the reduced section calculated by the DZC approach for a hole of $\varnothing 4\text{mm}$ is shown in Fig. 2 for the three sample types. The distributions for the quasi-isotropic and biomimetic laminates are nearly the same, with the former having a higher stress in the damage zone, corresponding to the higher unnotched strength.

Fig. 3 illustrates the fracture observed in the samples with a $\varnothing 4\text{mm}$ hole. The pictures are also fairly representative of the different fracture patterns observed in the samples with the $\varnothing 5\text{mm}$ hole. The notched cross-ply laminate, like the unnotched sample, broke along a straight line, and the damage, involving mainly fiber breakage, was very localized. The locations of the fracture in the two legs of the reduced section were somewhat staggered. In the quasi-isotropic sample, the fracture ran at 45° from the hole, leading to a 90° V-shape. This was accompanied by delamination exposing mainly 45° layers and some loose debris of pulled-out delaminated layers. When the surface fibers were parallel to the sample's axis, extensive splitting occurred, while some spalling occurred for 0° surface layers. In the biomimetic laminate, the angle of the V-shaped fracture was larger, and much less splitting was observed in the surface layer with longitudinal fibers. Delamination exposed mainly layers with fibers at angles above 45° , leading to the conclusion that the other layers, at angles closer to 0° , failed by fiber breakage. The fact that more fiber breakage could be achieved at fracture for the biomimetic lay-up may explain the higher relative strength of the notched samples.

Fig. 2: Calculated stress profile at failure of samples with a 4mm diameter circular hole.

Fig. 3: Features of fracture in (from L to R) the cross-ply, quasi-isotropic, and biomimetic laminates with a central $\phi 4\text{mm}$ hole.

Keeping in mind its higher resistance to impact damage initiation [3], the higher notched strength ratio of the biomimetic laminate further contributes to its better overall damage tolerance compared to the standard quasi-isotropic laminate. The tradeoff for this increase in performance is the higher complexity of the lay-up, requiring more care during production. With current automated, computer-controlled manufacturing methods, this should however be a minor problem when increased damage tolerance is really desired.

CONCLUSIONS

The plain and notched strength of a biomimetic laminate with a reinforcement architecture similar to that used in biological composites has been examined and compared to the strength of conventional quasi-isotropic and cross-ply laminates. For plain samples without a hole, the modulus of the biomimetic laminate is about the same as that of the quasi-isotropic one, and its strength is only slightly lower. Both have a lower strength than the cross-ply laminate. When a hole is introduced into the laminate, the strength of the biomimetic laminate is decreased less than that of the quasi-isotropic, and much less than for the cross-ply laminate. This higher strength ratio and the larger size of a calculated equivalent damage zone indicates a somewhat superior damage tolerance of the biomimetic laminate under tension. This quality is more pronounced for the larger hole size in the present investigation. It is proposed to be a result of the broader distribution of fiber angles leading to a wider range of interlaminar stresses near the edges and hole. As the biomimetic laminate is also more impact resistant, its overall damage tolerance is clearly better than the conventional quasi-isotropic laminate.

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REFERENCES

1. Neville, A.C., *The Biology of Fibrous Composites: Development Beyond the Cell Membrane*, Cambridge University Press, 1993.

2. Giraud, M.M., Castanet, J., Meunier, F.J., Bouligand, Y., The fibrous structure of coelacanth scales: a twisted 'plywood', *Tissue and Cell*, Vol. 10, No. 4, pp. 671-686, 1978.
3. Gunderson, S.L., Whitney, J.M., A controlled unsymmetric ply orientation for improved isotropic properties, *Advances in Experimental Mechanics*, ASME Vol. AMD-146, pp. 99-109, 1992.
4. Li, S., Zhang, R., Fu, S., Chen, X., Zhou, B., Zeng, Q., A biomimetic model of fiber-reinforced composite materials, *Journal of Materials Science and Technology*, Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 34-38, 1994.
5. Eriksson, I., Aronsson, C.-G., Strength of tensile-loaded graphite/epoxy laminates containing cracks, open and filled holes, *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 24, No. 5, pp. 456-482, 1990.
6. Chang, K.-Y., Liu, S., Chang, F.-K., *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 25, pp. 274-301, 1991.